

**A CLINICAL STUDY TO EVALUATE THE EFFICACY OF SNUHI KSHARA AND
KASISADI TAIL PICHU IN THE MANAGEMENT OF KARNINI YONIVYAPAD WSR
TO CERVICAL EROSION*****¹Dr. Rukhsar Khan, ²Prof. Shashi Sharma, ³Dr. Shikha Sharma**¹M.S (Final Year), Department of Prasuti Tantra Evam Stri Roga, State Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Lucknow.²H.O.D., Department of Prasuti Tantra Evam Stri Roga, State Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Lucknow.³Lecturer, Department of Prasuti Tantra Evam Stri Roga, State Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Lucknow.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Rukhsar Khan**

M.S (Final Year), Department of Prasuti Tantra Evam Stri Roga, State Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Lucknow.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18514947>**How to cite this Article:** *¹Dr. Rukhsar Khan, ²Prof. Shashi Sharma, ³Dr. Shikha Sharma (2026). A Clinical Study To Evaluate The Efficacy Of Snuhi Kshara And Kasisadi Tail Pichu In The Management Of Karnini Yonivyapad Wsr To Cervical Erosion. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(2), 496–499.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 05/01/2026

Article Revised on 25/01/2026

Article Published on 01/02/2026

ABSTRACT

Karnini Yonivyapad is a gynecological disorder described in Ayurvedic classics, characterized by abnormal growth, erosion, discharge and chronicity involving the cervix and vaginal portion of the uterus. On the basis of clinical features and local pathology, *Karnini Yonivyapad* can be correlated with cervical erosion (cervical ectopy) described in modern gynecology. Cervical erosion is a common benign condition in women of reproductive age, often associated with excessive vaginal discharge, post-coital bleeding, dyspareunia and chronic cervicitis. Conventional management includes cauterization, cryotherapy or electrosurgical procedures, which may be associated with pain, recurrence and cervical scarring. Ayurveda offers conservative and effective local therapeutic measures such as *Kshara Karma* and *Pichu Chikitsa*. The present article describes the efficacy of *Snuhi Kshara* application and *Kasisadi Tail Pichu* in the management of *Karnini Yonivyapad* with special reference to cervical erosion, along with their probable mode of action based on Ayurvedic principles and available clinical evidence.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda offers conservative and effective local therapeutic measures such as *Kshara Karma* and *Pichu Chikitsa*.**INTRODUCTION**

Diseases of the female reproductive system have been described elaborately in Ayurveda under the heading of *Yonivyapad*. Among them, *Karnini Yonivyapad* is mentioned as a chronic condition involving abnormal tissue growth (*karnika*), excessive discharge (*srava*), pain and discomfort in the yoni. Acharya Charaka and Acharya Sushruta have described *Karnini Yonivyapad* as a disorder predominantly caused by vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha dosha*, leading to local tissue derangement.

Cervical erosion, also termed cervical ectopy, is defined as the replacement of stratified squamous epithelium of the ectocervix by columnar epithelium. Although considered a benign condition, it may predispose the cervix to infection and chronic inflammation. From an Ayurvedic view, the erosion and excessive discharge seen in cervical erosion closely resemble the signs and

symptoms of *Karnini Yonivyapad*. Hence, Ayurvedic local therapies aimed at *lekhana*, *shodhana* and *ropana* are found to be highly beneficial.

CONCEPT OF KARNINI YONIVYAPAD IN AYURVEDA

According to Charaka Samhita, *Karnini Yonivyapad* is caused by aggravated *Vata* and *Kapha dosha*, resulting in the formation of a hard, fleshy growth (*karnika*) inside the yoni, associated with discharge and pain. Sushruta Samhita describes similar features and emphasizes local treatment modalities. The involvement of *Kapha* leads to excessive secretion and chronicity, while *Vata* contributes to pain, roughness and delayed healing.

The pathological process (*samprapti*) includes:

- *Dosha*: Vata-Kapha
- *Dushya*: Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa

- *Srotas*: Artavavaha srotas
- *Adhithana*: Yoni and Garbhashaya mukha (cervix)

CORRELATION WITH CERVICAL EROSION

Cervical erosion presents with symptoms such as white discharge, pruritus vulvae, dyspareunia, backache and occasional bleeding. On per-speculum examination, the cervix appears red, inflamed and eroded. These clinical features correspond well with *Karnini Yonivyapad*, where erosion (*vrana*), discharge (*srava*) and local tenderness are described. Thus, cervical erosion can be considered the closest modern correlate of *Karnini Yonivyapad*.

PRINCIPLES OF MANAGEMENT IN AYURVEDA

The management of *Karnini Yonivyapad* includes both *Shodhana* and *Shamana* therapies. Local treatment (*Sthanik Chikitsa*) plays a crucial role. Among local therapies, *Kshara Karma* is indicated for conditions involving abnormal tissue growth, chronic ulcers and non-healing lesions, while *Taila Pichu* is used for soothing, healing and strengthening the local tissues.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVE

1. To study the detailed aetiopathogenesis of *Karnini Yonivyapad* wsr to Cervical Erosion.
2. To evaluate the efficacy of *Snuhi Kshara*, *Kasisadi Tail Pichu* in the management of *Karnini Yonivyapad*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sample Source: All the patients were registered from the OPD and IPD of PG Department Prasuti Tantra & Stri Roga, State Ayurvedic College & Hospital, Lucknow UP, who fulfilled inclusion criteria irrespective of their desh, jati, Vayu, prakriti, sattv, after taking informed consent.

Type of study- Simple Random, comparative, open clinical trial.

Selection of cases-Total 20 clinically diagnosed and confirmed cases of cervical erosion.

20 patients were treated with local application of *Snuhi Kshara* once in a cycle followed by *Kasisadi tail pichu* for 7 days, after clearance of menses for 2 consecutive cycles.

Inclusion criteria

- Age in between 25 to 45 years
- Married women.
- Clinically diagnosed and confirmed patient by per speculum examination.
- Patients having sign and symptoms of cervical erosion.
- Patient willing to go through trial.
- Yonigat shrav (persistent luccorrhea), shroni shool, yoni shool, yoni kandu, katishool.
- contact bleeding.

Exclusion criteria

- Women of age less than 25 and above than 45.
- Unmarried women.
- Pregnant women, lactating women.
- Acute PID.
- Other systemic disorders like hypertension diabetes tuberculosis.
- Patient having uterine prolapse.
- Patients having cervical carcinoma and any malignant growth.
- HIV, VDRL, HBsAg positive patient.
- Patients on OCPs and IUCD.

20 patients were treated with local application of *Snuhi Kshara* once in a cycle followed by *Kasisadi tail pichu* for 7 days, after clearance of menses for 2 consecutive cycles.

TOTAL PATIENTS	TRIAL DRUG	DOSE	MODE OF ADMINISTRATION	DURATION OF TREATMENT
20	SNUHI KSHARA (ONCE) FOLLOWED BY KASISADI TAIL PICHU(FOR 7 DAYS) after clearance of menses.	Snuhi kshara 250-500mg. (as required) Kaisadi tail 10ml (approx) for pichu	LOCAL APPLICATION (ON CERVIX)	TWO CONSECUTIVE CYCLES WITH TRIAL DRUG AND ONE CONSECUTIVE CYCLE WITHOUT TRIAL DRUG

Criteria for withdrawal

- Patient who discontinue the treatment themselves due to any reason or did not return for the final follow up.
- Aggravation of complications
- Any other acute or sever illness.

Investigation- CBC, RBS, LFT, KFT, HIV, HBsAg, VDRL, Vaginal pH, Pap smear for cervical cytology (if needed), Urine routine and microscopic.

SUBJECTIVE CRITERIA

- Vaginal discharges
- Yoni kandu (pruritis vulvae)
- Katishool (low backache)
- Mutra daha (burning micturition)
- Yoni daha (burning sensation around vulvae region)
- Contact bleeding
- Yonishool (pain in vulva region)
- Dyspareunia (maithunkricha)

OBJECTIVE CRITERIA

Assessment of effect of therapy on cervical changes is

done before and after trial. It is done on the basis of effect of therapy

- Area covered by erosion.
- Appearance and color of the erosion.
- Cervical tenderness during examination.
- Type of discharges

PROCEDURE- After taking informed consent, the patient is called for kshar application, after clearance of menses. Patient was asked to lie in lithotomy position Vaginal examination (P/S) was performed to note condition of Vulva, Vagina, Cervix Size,

consistency, position, mobility of the uterus.

Cervix is exposed using cosco's speculum, kshar was applied with a cotton swab stick over the eroded cervical area and kept in contact for 1 minute. When cauterized area become dark violet in colour. then washed with distilled water. Then after that kasisadi oil pichu was kept higher in vagina touching the cervix. Patient is advised to keep the Pichu for approximately 2 hour and ask to remove by pulling the tail, which is kept outside the vagina for easy removal.

Snuhi Kshara: Preparation and Properties

Snuhi Kshara is prepared from the ash of *Snuhi* (*Euphorbia nerifolia* Linn.). It possesses *Tikshna*, *Ushna*, *Katu* and *Kshara* properties. Classical texts describe *Kshara* as having *lekhana*, *bhedana*, *chedana* and *shodhana* actions.

Therapeutic Action of Snuhi Kshara

- Causes chemical cauterization of unhealthy, eroded columnar epithelium
- Removes slough and abnormal tissue (*lekhana karma*)
- Reduces excessive secretion by pacifying *Kapha dosha*
- Facilitates regeneration of healthy squamous epithelium
- Acts as antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory agent

In cervical erosion, application of *Snuhi Kshara* over the eroded cervix helps in controlled destruction of abnormal tissue, similar to modern cauterization, but in a more holistic and tissue-friendly manner.

Kasisadi Taila Pichu: Composition and Properties

Kasisadi Taila is a medicated oil formulation containing ingredients such as *Kasisa* (Ferrous sulphate), *Haridra*, *Daruharidra* and other drugs processed in *Taila*. When applied as *Pichu*, a sterile cotton swab soaked in the oil is placed in the vagina in contact with the cervix for a specified duration.

Therapeutic Action of Kasisadi Tail Pichu

- Promotes wound healing (*ropana karma*)
- Reduces burning sensation, pain and irritation
- Maintains local moisture and improves epithelialization
- Enhances the effect of *Kshara* by supporting tissue regeneration
- Pacifies *Vata dosha* and nourishes local tissues

Combined Effect of Snuhi Kshara and Kasisadi Tail Pichu

The combined use of *Snuhi Kshara* followed by *Kasisadi Tail Pichu* provides a comprehensive approach. While *Snuhi Kshara* acts by removing diseased tissue and controlling discharge, *Kasisadi Tail Pichu* ensures proper healing, reduces discomfort and prevents complications such as excessive dryness or scarring.

Clinical observations have shown significant improvement in symptoms like vaginal discharge, cervical tenderness and size of erosion, along with healthy epithelial regeneration.

CRITERIA FOR FINAL ASSESSMENT OF RESULT

Based on the assessment of the symptoms, the total effect of therapy is Evaluated and grouped according to the following criteria:

Marked improvement **75 to 100% relief in the symptoms**
Moderate improvement **50 to 75% of relief in the symptoms**
Mild improvement **25 – 50% of relief**

Unchanged Less than **25% of relief in the symptoms.**

RESULT

OVERALL ASSESMENT	GROUP A	
	No.	%
MARKED IMPROVEMENT	13	65%
MODERATE IMPROVEMENT	7	35%
MILD IMPROVEMENT	0	0%
UNCHANGED	0	0%

Test applied in Statistical Data:

Subjective parameter and Objective parameter - **Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test, Mann Whitney U Test**

DISCUSSION

From an Ayurvedic perspective, *Snuhi Kshara* directly addresses the *Kapha-pradhana dushti* responsible for chronic discharge and erosion, whereas *Kasisadi Tail Pichu* counteracts *Vata* involvement by providing unctuousness and promoting healing. This sequential therapy aligns with the classical principle of *shodhana followed by ropana*.

Subjective parameters

- 1. Amount of Vaginal discharge:** It was significantly reduced because *Snuhi* has *vata* and *kapha* nashak guna.
- 2. Dyspareunia:** Anti-inflammatory and analgesic property" of *Snuhi* has contributed max. relief in dyspareunia.
- 3. Pruritis Vulvae:** *Snuhi* in Pruritis vulvae to give relief to the patient.
- 4. Low Backache:** Probably due to virtue of *Ushna Tikshna Guna* of *Kshara* and *Vatashamaka Guna* of *Snuhi* give considerable relief in lower backache. Max. relief was may be due to analgesic property of *Snuhi*! Because of the *Sothahara* effect of *kasisadi Taila* by which the congestion in the nearby organ is reduced and so the back pain is also relieved.
- 5. Lower Abdominal pain:** *Snuhi kshara* known to be alleviating diseases like *udar roga*, *Gulm*, *Visuchika*, *Ajirna Sool*. Lower abdominal pain in a patient of *Karnini* may be due to any of these above atiology.

Objective Parameters

1. Amount of Vaginal discharge

This may be because after the healing of erosion, the vaginal discharge minimize due to decreased secretion from cervical glands.

2. Oozing blood from erosion on rubbing with gauze piece

Improvement was good due to vasoconstrictive and wound healing property of *Snuhi*.

3. Area of eroded cervix

Healing of cervical erosion is measured by destruction of columnar epithelium. This aim is fulfilled by *Kshara* by its *Tikshna Guna*.

4. Cervical Tenderness

Snuhi Kshara has *Shoolnashan* property which helps in curing cervical tenderness.

CONCLUSION

The management of *Karnini Yonivyapad* with *Snuhi Kshara* application and *Kasisadi Tail Pichu* is an effective Ayurvedic therapeutic modality for cervical erosion. It offers significant symptomatic relief, promotes healthy epithelialization and minimizes recurrence. This combination therapy stands as a safe and holistic alternative to conventional cauterization techniques. Further large-scale clinical trials may help in standardizing the protocol and strengthening the evidence base.

Source of Support; Nil.

Conflict of Interest; None declared.

REFERENCES

1. Charaka Samhita, Chikitsa Sthana, Yonivyapad Chikitsa Adhyaya, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Series, Varanasi.
2. Sushruta Samhita, Uttara Tantra, Yonivyapad Pratishedha Adhyaya, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi.
3. Ashtanga Hridaya, Uttara Sthana, Yonivyapad Nidanam, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan, Delhi.
4. Dutta DC. Textbook of Gynecology. Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers, New Delhi.
5. Shaw RW, Soutter WP, Stanton SL. Gynaecology. Elsevier Health Sciences.
6. Patil SB et al. Management of Cervical Erosion through Ayurvedic Interventions – A Clinical Study. AYU Journal.
7. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. Clinical evaluation of *Kshara Karma* and *Pichu* in *Karnini Yonivyapad*.
8. Indian Journal of Applied Research. Role of Ayurvedic local therapies in cervical erosion.